

SOCPacific
A Sea of Connections

Combining interviews and focus group *talanoa* for understanding reef passage governance on Ovalau island, Fiji, in 2025

Study report

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1. Introduction to the project and research context

Reef passages are natural breaks in reefs that connect the coastal zones to the open ocean. As hotspots for biodiversity reproductivity, and as pathways for fisher(wo)men as well as a variety of non-human species, they hold remarkable value for environment and society.

The project SOCPacific2R designs its research activities using an empirical inter- and transdisciplinary approach, combining natural and social sciences methods, and focuses on reef passages in Fiji and New Caledonia. The project aims to:

1. Conducting a transdisciplinary study of reef passages as under-researched features of social-ecological coral reef systems that constitute complex, interconnected, and dynamic assemblages of living and non-living, dwelling and transiting, entities that interact with each other;
2. Documenting both area-based and other management and conservation arrangements applied to reef passages, including the pros and cons that local stakeholder groups identify;
3. Establishing a participatory science-society-policy dialogue informed by social-ecological studies, Oceanian socio-cosmologies and sovereignties, and governance norms in/for the management and conservation of reef passages.

SOCPacific2R works with various stakeholders to achieve the project's goals: scientists, administrators, NGOs, and local communities. The outcomes of the project will feed into wider frameworks on marine sustainability such as the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030).

Local communities are the main knowledge holders and users of the reef passages that surround the Fijian and New Caledonian islands. The presented study aimed to learn their perspectives and experiences concerning the reef passages on Ovalau island in Fiji through an interdisciplinary research team, and was conducted by a student group of the University of the South Pacific (USP) between September 2025 and February 2026.

2. Research Methodology

During our field work on Ovalau island, Fiji, semi-structured interviews and focus group *talanoa* (space for inclusive Pacific Island dialogue)¹ were combined to produce data about

¹ From Kaitapu et al. (2026): "According to Matapo and Enari (2021:80), *talanoa* is defined as "a phenomenological Pacific research framework that affirms Pacific thinking, language and culture", even though it is not a generic or universal concept within the South Pacific region. It refers to an exchange of knowledge and ways of thinking, whether it is formal and informal, without a rigid framework, and "allows people to engage in social conversation which may lead to critical discussions or knowledge creation that allows

the customary protected area (locally known as a *tabu* area) related to Toki Passage in Vatukalo Village’s waters, while valuing the expertise on this topic of local knowledge holders (both women and men). These two methods were employed to explore specific themes that emerge both at an individual level and in collective discussions.

The semi-structured interviews were done in a more relaxed and informal setting like a private home of the interviewee, compared to the focus group talanoa held at a communal space. In the latter, social protocols of behaviour can prevent especially younger participants from expressing their views openly in the presence of respected elderly. While the interviews provided the participants with the opportunity to share their personal experiences as well as sensitive viewpoints, the focus group talanoa helped the researchers gather shared meanings, different societal dynamics and community perspectives. Together, these methods strengthened the project by balancing collective narratives with individual views, thereby producing a nuanced understanding of the studied *tabu*.

Figure 1: Timeline of applied methods in this study.

2.1 Semi-structured interviews

A total of 17 semi-structured interviews with altogether 15 participants were conducted across two sites/villages: Levuka Vakaviti and Vatukalo villages (Table 1). 16 interviews were carried out in Vatukalo, five with women and eleven with men, including two follow-up interviews. In Levuka Vakaviti, one interview was conducted with a local leader.

Table 1: Interview participants by age and gender.

Age & Gender	33 f	40 f	51 f	54 f	58 f	30 m	40 m	48 m	56 m	59 m	60 m	63 m	64 m	66 m
First round Interview							X	X	X	X			X	X
Second round Interview	X	X	X	X	X	X		X		X	X	X		

rich contextual and inter-related information to surface as co-constructive stories” (Vaioleti 2006:24). Non-human actors are also acknowledged as “powerful actors in talanoa (Matapo and Enari 2021:86).”

Interviews were conducted between late September and early December 2025, with Free Prior Informed Consent from all participants. Overall, people from diverse backgrounds were interviewed, such as chiefs, fish wardens, fishers and committee representatives. The participants were 30 - 66 years old and were asked about information on the *tabu* area between the Waitovu and Toki reef passages.

The participants were recruited through advice by the village headman (Turaga ni Koro) and other community members. The interviews lasted between 30 and 60 minutes using an interview guide focusing on five thematic areas: environmental aspects, governance, spirituality, management challenges and socio-economic factors (Attachment 1).

The interviews were usually done in the comfort of the participants' house, yet some interviewees suggested community spaces. Participants were approached at an appropriate time, through the Turaga ni Koro ensuring local protocols are being met. Most interviews were conducted in iTaukei (Fijian) language, two interviewees combined English and iTaukei in their answers. All interviews were audio-recorded, taken with their verbal permission, and notes were also taken to capture keywords and important contextual information (Woodsong et al., 2005). The transcriptions were done in the spoken language, the text in iTaukei was translated to English.

The data was analyzed with the same thematic lenses like the interviews, each topic to address the objectives of the study. The qualitative analysis of the data was done manually and analytically by organizing the transcription into the five thematic fields. Coding was applied to extract shared knowledge on these topics. For each different theme, we compared the similarities and differences in local views through a gender-age lens.

The findings were compiled to produce thematic summaries supported by quotes from interviewees, then shared with local communities at Tokou, Vatukalo and Levuka town in November 2025 (preliminary results) and February 2026 (final results) in poster forms.

2.2 Talanoa – Focus Group Discussions in a Pacific Island Dialogue format

To gain a deeper understanding into collective perceptions and lived experiences about the *tabu* area between Waitovu and Toki reef passages, two focus group talanoa was conducted with knowledge holders of Vatukalo Village. This qualitative data collection allows participants to share viewpoints both among themselves and with the researcher, through interactive group conversations. Therefor facilitating the talanoa, where participants share collective knowledge, allows the researcher to document the shared experiences from the discussions (Woodsong et al., 2005)

The talanoa were done in Vatukalo village with women and men separately both in December 2025. The goal was to have at least five participants per each group to ensure representation of different views. Six women aged 19 to 57 and seven men aged between 26 and 48 participated in the talanoa groups.

The participant groups comprised of people from diverse backgrounds, including fishermen, fisherwomen, male and female clan leaders and other community members, ensuring a rich variety of perspectives on reef passages, their governance, fishing activities and the *tabu*

area. The two focus group talanoa were held in two different places and at different times, the women at the community hall and the men at the Turaga ni Koro's house. These two places were carefully chosen to minimize distractions and ensure comfort and respect while participants from both groups enjoyed their kava while taking part in the discussions. The kava ceremony functions as an essential part of communal gathering and creates an open space for informal and trusted conversation. The session lasted around 50 minutes allowing sufficient time to generate perspectives while exploring each of the topics.

Prior to the interview, the participants were informed about the purpose of the research centered around *tabu* area in the broader context of the study on valuing reefs passages. Consent to make recordings of the sessions for data analysis purposes was granted by the groups. Adding on, to ensure their voluntary participation, they were also instructed that it is within their right to withdraw at any time. Confidentiality was assured as pseudonyms are used in the transcriptions and results presentations.

A set of open-ended questions was used to explore key thematic areas like environmental factors, governance and spirituality to address specific objectives relevant to the research study with probing to ensure flexibility and clarity between the dialogues (Woodsong et al., 2005).

Both talanoa were facilitated by the researcher who guided the sessions using a discussion guide based on the same questions as the interviews. Open dialogue was encouraged to start the conversations. Probing was also used to clarify information that was not clear and give participants the opportunity to contextualize their experiences into their own words.

We conducted a thematic analysis of the qualitative data from the focus group talanoa, with a specific lens on gender and age. Transcribing the recordings (in the same manner as the interviews) and going through the notes was important to add familiarity with the data and grouping them into categories supported by quotes to compile thematic summaries. This supported interpreting the patterns of meaning in comparison with the interviews. The outcomes were presented back to the community in February 2026.

Sources & References

Kaitapu, M., Bishwa, D., Manulevu, S.-F., & Nata, W. (2026). Drawing as a participatory method alongside interviews and 'talanoa' to understand children's views of reef passages on Ovalau island, Fiji, in 2025. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18860411>

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